

Navigating the Future of Rural Connectivity: The XGAIN Tool Architecture

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In an era where digital transformation is pivotal, the European XGAIN project [1] emerges as a beacon of innovation, especially for addressing rural connectivity challenges. This project aims to provide assessment on how to implement technical infrastructure deployments to introduce this digital transformation, focusing on rural areas' unique needs. The Knowledge Facilitation Tool (KFT), a central element of XGAIN, stands at the forefront of this change.

Scope and Challenges of the XGAIN project

The primary objective of the XGAIN project is to involve and understand stakeholders' needs, primarily focusing on stakeholders from rural areas who are facing the particular challenges of the digital divide: Whereas in cities and more populated areas state of the art technologies like 5G are easily accessible, rural areas in general lag behind, just having access to previous connectivity generations like 3G or 4G, often with poor coverage. These differences can be explained by the lower expected turnover for mobile network operators, which does not justify large-scale infrastructure deployments. Further, challenging types of terrain like mountains make deployments more costly and they can heavily impair radio communications, reducing the potential coverage.

To provide guidance for a wide range of necessities that emerge from services specific for rural areas, the KFT considers a wide variety of types of end devices, radio communication technologies and computing technologies. Drones, IoT sensors, and cameras are typical end devices that enable novel services, and which can benefit from state-of-the-art communication technology deployments: high performing communications, like 5G, ubiquitous technologies like satellite communications, or narrowband IoT communications for sensors; all of them are considered by the KFT, to name a few.

The KFT, designed as a Human-Machine Interface (HMI), plays a pivotal role in the process of providing a better understanding of how these technologies can close this gap, considering the main challenges that arise from rural environments. The KFT, via a user-friendly dashboard, offers suggestions for technical deployments including connectivity and computation elements, addressing the critical need for enhanced connectivity in these regions for specific sectors and services. The project faces numerous challenges, including the diverse and specific needs of rural stakeholders and the complexity of assessing varied technological solutions into a cohesive system. In this process, the KFT provides techno-economical and socio-environmental assessment to understand how a technical solution could impact on a farm, community or even at regional levels. As such, the KFT's architectural design needs to be able to properly tackle all these challenges.

Methodology for Requirement Elicitation and Analysis

The project adopts a systematic approach to define functional requirements (FRs) and non-functional requirements (NFRs) of the KFT in order to define the architecture. Key steps include requirement elicitation, where sources such as the project's scope (as per grant agreement), stakeholders' input,

and partners' expertise contribute to identifying potential requirements. Subsequent analysis consolidates and prioritizes these requirements, shaping the final architecture design. A significant part of this process involves collecting user stories, which are then translated into FRs and NFRs, guiding the architecture's development.

After specifying the requirements and analyzing which ones are implemented, the KFT software architecture can be defined.

KFT Architecture Definition

The architecture of the KFT is defined through a four-step process:

1. **High-Level Design:** This involves outlining the main layers and components/modules of the KFT.
2. **Specification of Functional Blocks:** Each module's functional blocks are identified and specified. These blocks represent high-level functions that the KFT needs to implement.
3. **Primitives and Interfaces:** The supported primitives and interfaces for each block are determined.
4. **Interconnectivity:** Connections and interaction schemes among components are established.

This architecture is grounded in the FRs and NFRs identified earlier, ensuring that each element of the KFT aligns with the stakeholders' needs and project objectives. In the process of defining the features, a series of core functionalities have been mapped to functional blocks in the architecture. These include the requirement gathering, the technology mix finder, the dimensioning solver, the techno-economical and the socio-environmental analysis, as well as a business models proposer.

The requirement gathering module is where the user can specify the needs for the service that is to be deployed: information about the topography of an area and the meteorological conditions to be expected, but also questions about specifics of the service(s), e.g. which devices are to be used and which services are to be implemented. The key technical requirements are gathered in this initial step with user-friendly questions that do not require a deep understanding of the technologies considered by the KFT. Then, the technology mix finder, based on a large database of existing technologies for connectivity and processing, determines which technologies are suitable for the service(s), as specified by the user. For different combinations of technologies, the dimensioning solver then determines numbers of necessary infrastructure elements and the logical network overlay to satisfy the requirements of the service. In a next step, the techno-economical and the socio-environmental perform an assessment of over 30 key performance indicators, that cover technological, ecological, sustainability and social impact aspects to determine how the technology mixes score with regards to each category. Proper business models for the targeted services are added in the final step and presented together with the proposed technology mixes and the corresponding assessments.

With this definition of responsibilities for each of these modules and having identified their interaction patterns, the architecture diagram shown in Figure 1 has been identified. It includes additional breakdowns of the previously described modules.

Figure 1: KFT Architecture Diagram

First Design: The KFT Mockup

An integral part of the initial architecture design in the XGAIN project is the creation of the KFT mockup developed using the Figma tool. The mockup serves as design study, implementing a tangible and visual representation of the proposed dashboard and features. It facilitates stakeholder engagement and internal discussions, providing a visual and interactive medium to refine the KFT's functionalities. As an evolving element of the project, the mockup is updated every now and then with new or refined dashboard views, as the different lines of work in the project keep molding user interface aspects of the KFT. The current version of the mockup can be found [here](#) [2].

Final Challenges in Architecture Design and Future Work

The project has been navigating complexities in integrating diverse requirements into a unified architecture but is almost about to reach its conclusion. The iterative design process, from mockup creation to the final architecture, addressed these challenges. The use of methodologies like MoSCoW [3] for prioritization of features and the 5W1H analysis for architecture definition have played a crucial role in this context. The work done to define the architecture eventually serves as base for the actual implementation of the KFT which integrates the different modules discussed earlier. We invite the reader to follow the latest developments on the project website [1] and to contact us in case there are any questions, comments or suggestions.

References

[1] XGain Project, <https://xgain-project.eu/>

[2] [KFT Mockup Version](#) (November 2023)

[3] Agile Business Consortium: Chapter 10 MoSCoW Prioritization, January 2014. https://www.agilebusiness.org/page/ProjectFramework_10_MoSCoWPrioritisation. Accessed 10 Oct 2021

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A large, semi-transparent watermark of the XGain logo is centered on the page. The 'X' is a light teal color, while the 'Gain' is a light grey color. The signal icon above the 'X' is a light blue color.